

DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ABILITIES IN THE TRAINING OF SENIOR NURSES THROUGH THE STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE AND PROFESSIONAL MOBILITY

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ABSTRACT

The given article considers and analyzes the professional training of nurses as the largest component of the healthcare workforce; reveals the need to develop professional competence and professional mobility of nurses as the fundamental validity of the development of creative abilities in modern conditions; the definition of these concepts is given.

The concept of healthcare in the Republic of Uzbekistan has identified new requirements for the development of a system of professional training of medical personnel. Nursing is an important part of the health care workforce. The effective development of the healthcare system largely depends on the state of professional training of nurses as the largest component of the healthcare workforce.

The main system-forming concepts of training nurses in continuing professional education are “professional competence” and “professional mobility of a nurse.”

To determine the essence of these concepts, consider the definitions of these concepts from various scientific sources. Depending on the way in which the content of a concept is revealed, different types of definitions are distinguished in logic. The main ones most often used in scientific research are the following:

- a generic definition, which indicates the closest genus for the concept being defined and the distinctive features that are present only in a given type of object and are absent in all other types of objects included in this genus;
- a genetic definition, which indicates the origin of the item and the way in which the item is created;
- a real definition that reflects the essential features of an object, phenomenon and has as its goal to distinguish the defined object from all other objects by indicating its distinctive features;
- a nominal definition that explains the meaning of a term, often with the help of other, more familiar and therefore more understandable terms;
- an operational definition that represents an object through a description of the operations characteristic of it; Definitions of this kind are most often used at the beginning of the study of the properties of a particular object, when its essential and distinctive features have not yet been established or systematized¹.

To determine the essence of the concepts “professional competence of a nurse” and “professional competence of a nurse,” we first consider the concepts of “competence” and “competence” from various sources and highlight their characteristics. Then we will dwell on the definition of these concepts according to scientific sources that provide definitions of the competencies and competence of a nurse, we will also consider these concepts in accordance with the Federal State Educational Standard and then we will present our definition of these concepts.

Main part

Many foreign and domestic works are devoted to the problems of the competency-based approach, competencies and competence. The conceptual basis of the competency-based approach, a relatively new methodological toolkit in world practice and education, is the idea of competencies and key competencies, formed in foreign social theory as one of the most effective ways to resolve contradictions in the development of education and society, which confronts a person with the need to be competent in many related areas of activity and constantly update your knowledge throughout your life.

A special contribution to the development of the theory of the competence approach was made by V.I. Bidenko and I.A. Zimnyaya and other scientists. IN AND. Bidenko summarized foreign and domestic experience in theoretical understanding of the competency-based approach to higher education. He notes that the strengthening of cognitive and information principles in modern production is not “covered” by the traditional concept of “qualification”, but the concepts

“qualification” and “competence” seem to be more adequate. IN AND. Bidenko provides in his works a comparative analysis of the qualification and competence approaches, emphasizing that “competence is a measure of an individual’s educational success, manifested in his own actions in certain professional and socially significant situations, and qualification is a measure of an individual’s educational success, representing within its capabilities” [2].

Table 1 - Content analysis of the concept “competence”

No	Source	Definition
1	Ozhegov S.I., Shvedova N.Yu. Explanatory dictionary of the Russian language. – M., 1993. – P. 294.	Competencies are a range of issues, phenomena in which a given person has authority, knowledge, and experience.
2	Bidenko V.I. Competencies in higher professional education (towards the development of a competency-based approach) // Higher. education in Russia. – 2004. - No. 11. – P. 10.	Competence is a measure of an individual’s educational success, manifested in his own actions in certain professional and socially significant situations, and qualification is a measure of an individual’s educational success,
3	Zeer E.F. Psychology of professional development. – M., 2007. – P. 135.	representing in its capabilities.

4	Zimnyaya I.A. Key competencies - a new paradigm for educational results // Higher. education today -	Competencies are generalized methods of action that ensure the productive performance of professional activities. This is a person's ability to practically realize his
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The analysis allows us, on the one hand, to highlight the signs of competence and compare the concepts of “competence” and “competence”.

Among the signs of competence, we highlight the following: a person's ability to work in a particular field, possessing a certain system of knowledge and skills, and a person's readiness for professional activity.

A comparison of the concepts “competence” and “competence” shows that both of these terms are close, as they come from the same root English words “competence” and “competency”, but are often characterized by different interpretations in the Russian version; Both concepts are broader than just knowledge, skills and abilities, as they include:

- a set of personality qualities possessing value-motivational abilities;
- willingness to overcome stereotypes in activities;
- flexibility of thinking, independence and determination.

The concept of “competence” implies the unification of knowledge, skills and abilities that determine a person's ability to act, and “competence” represents an integrative quality of a person, including cognitive, practical and value components;

The concept of “competence” allows us to highlight the complex integrative ability of an individual when solving professional problems based on experience and competencies.

Solving the problem of developing the professional competence of a medical worker involves relying on the analysis of the complex and diverse professional activities of a specialist. The research of A.P. is devoted to identifying the psychological basis of this activity. Belova, T.A. Kavelina, L.A. Korchinsky et al. As these studies show, one of the important components is the nursing process - the organization and provision of nursing care in the interaction between the patient and the nurse. The professional qualities of a nurse determine the productivity of her work.

I.S. Vitenko defines the following professionally important qualities of a nurse:

- moral: compassion; goodwill; hard work; optimism; determination;
- aesthetic: neatness; neatness; attraction to festivity;
- intellectual: erudition, observation, logic⁶.

In my opinion, the author in this definition does not take into account an important component of the professional competence of a nurse - professional knowledge and skills, without which competence is impossible.

Zh.V. Komarova identifies the following components in the professional competence of a medical worker: “1) professional knowledge (according to state educational standards of secondary vocational education, 2002); professional activity; professionally important personality traits⁷

Considering the professional development of the personality of a mid-level medical worker, E.A. Bastrakova identifies several substructures of professionally important qualities, knowledge, abilities and skills of a medical specialist. The first substructure - professional motives, interests, beliefs - expresses the attitude of the individual medical specialist to the

activities performed. The second substructure determines the individual properties of the physician's personality, which are based on the psychological properties of the individual (temperament, character, abilities), which determine the individual's behavior in various life and professional situations. In the substructure of professionally important qualities, the author identifies both general, basic ones (hard work, discipline, initiative, organization, etc.) and special ones, determined by the characteristics of a particular profession [8].

For our study, an important indicator of the professional development of a nurse is her psychological readiness for professional activity. Psychological readiness of E.A. Bastrakova defines it as "a stable characteristic of an individual, an essential prerequisite for purposeful activity, which allows an individual to fulfill his professional duties, using existing experience, knowledge, personal qualities, and also to restructure his activities in unforeseen professional situations [9].

Let us limit ourselves to these works, which, in our opinion, highlight quite complete signs of professional competence of a nurse.

In the works we studied on the professional training of nurses, we did not find any special studies devoted to the disclosure of the concept of "professional mobility of a nurse." There are only separate fragments that allow the researcher to be guided towards the disclosure of this concept.

Conclusion

Currently, vocational education is based on the implementation of a model of advanced education, which is based on the idea of personal development. Advanced education, in contrast to traditional education, focuses in the training of specialists not so much on specific professional activities, but on the formation of readiness to master new knowledge, the acquisition of multifunctional skills "

Based on the analysis of the above works and our practical experience, the professional mobility of a nurse represents an integral dynamic quality of a specialist, based on his readiness for professional activities and determining the specialist's adaptation to new conditions and types of activities, responsibility in decision-making and the ability for self-development.

Thus, in the concept of "professional mobility of a nurse" we highlight several important components. The first is related to the readiness of the nurse for professional activities, which is reflected in the professional competence of the specialist. To be mobile, a nurse must be able to adapt to new conditions: medical, social and medical institutions, governing bodies, be able to use innovative technologies and equipment in professional activities - this is determined by her adaptability. A mobile nurse must not only be able to adapt to new conditions, but also take responsibility for independently making certain decisions; this reflects responsibility as a quality of a specialist's personality. Finally, in order to be mobile, a nurse needs to constantly improve, self-develop and realize herself both in her professional activities and in the professional community.

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